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Development of Human Energy Harvester Using Piezoelectric Materials

Arinola Bola AJAYI^{1*}, Temitope Elizabeth OYEKANMI¹, Emmanuel Kolawole OLOWOPOROKU¹, Adeshola Oluremi Openibo², Musiliu Olalekan ADEYINKA¹, Babatunde Anthony ASAOLU¹, Ibrahim Ayinla MAHMUD¹.

¹Mechanical Engineering Department,
Faculty of Engineering,
University of Lagos, Lagos. Nigeria

²Mechanical Engineering Department,
Faculty of Engineering,
Lagos State University, Epe Campus. Lagos State. Nigeria

*Corresponding author: abajayi@unilag.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This research work explores how to capture energy from human movement and convert it into usable electrical power that can be stored and utilized later. The research employs the method of utilizing the principle of piezoelectricity to harvest human energy from human footsteps. A model for the piezoelectric energy harvester that works with impact of human footfalls were developed. Energy harvesting is one of the most effective ways to respond to the increasing demand of energy and to produce sustainable power sources from the surrounding environment without polluting the environment. Piezoelectric energy harvester serves as a means of renewable energy and can be employed in densely populated areas for continuous generation of electricity. Piezoelectric energy harvesting uses a direct energy conversion of vibrations and mechanical deformation (gotten from walking on the energy harvester) to produce electrical energy. Experimental results indicated that integrating piezoelectric elements into human activities can yield significant power outputs for low-energy devices. Making use of 84 piezoelectric transducers, 10 LEDs were lit up. It was found that the amount of energy generated varies linearly with increasing weight of persons stepping on the energy harvester, number of persons stepping on it, and the number of piezoelectric harvesters employed in the device.

Keywords: Energy harvester, Footfalls, Human Energy, Piezoelectric crystals, Transducers, Vibration.

1. INTRODUCTION

The pursuit of sustainable and self-sufficient energy sources has led to significant interest in energy harvesting technologies, particularly those that can harness the ubiquitous mechanical energy generated by human movement [1]. Piezoelectric materials, which convert mechanical stress into electrical energy, offer a promising avenue for capturing this energy and powering wearable electronics, sensors, and other low-power devices [2]. Human motion, whether it be walking, running, or even subtle movements, presents a readily available and renewable energy source that can be exploited through piezoelectric energy harvesters [3]. The development of efficient and comfortable human energy harvesters necessitates careful consideration of material selection, device design, and integration with the human body [4]. This exploration of piezoelectric energy harvesting focuses on the design considerations, materials, and applications of these devices, highlighting the potential for

self-powered wearable technology. This paper investigates the development of a human energy harvester using piezoelectric materials, focusing on the conversion of mechanical energy from human motion into usable electrical energy. This study highlights both the potential applications and the challenges for scalability and long-term durability, suggesting directions for future improvement and integration into wearable electronics. Piezoelectricity, an innate attribute of ceramic materials, was discovered by Pierre and Jacques Curie in the year 1880. Skoog [5] defined piezoelectricity as the property of certain materials to produce electrical potential when subjected to mechanical stress. Some natural piezoelectric materials include DNA, enamel, silk, dentin, etc. Single crystals, like quartz, ZnO and synthetic crystalline materials, and ceramics like barium titanate, lead titanate, lead zirconate titanate, sodium potassium niobate, bismuth titanate, etc., and polymers like polyvinylidene fluoride, are found to exhibit this property [6]. Electrically-charged particles in substances are distributed in space in such a way that the opposed charges cancel each other out. This makes matter electrically-balanced so that they do not have excess electrical charge and are, hence, neutral. When mechanical strain is produced in the form of a physical deformation, certain materials undergo a forced-charge unbalance at their surfaces, which we term 'piezoelectricity'. Electrical energy is created from this forced-charge produced at the surfaces, this electrical energy can be used up at once or saved for later use, and this is achieved using a piezoelectric energy harvester. Figure 1 shows the change in the position of the atoms due to applied stress leading to the formation of net dipole moments (polarization) and an electric field

Figure 1. Showing net dipole moments (polarization) and an electric field.

A piezoelectric energy harvester is used to produce electricity from mechanical vibrations which can be gotten from footfalls, vehicles, rainfalls etc. with the effect of piezoelectricity. It generates electrical energy from mechanical stresses applied on it. The energy that will be produced from the energy harvester depends on the amount of force applied to it. The greater the force applied the greater the electrical energy that will be produced. It serves as a means of renewable energy, converting expended mechanical energy to useful electrical energy that can either be stored for later use or used immediately. Piezoelectric materials can be natural or man-made. The natural PEM are crystal materials like quartz (SiO_2), Rochelle salt, Topaz, Tourmaline-group minerals and some organic substances as silk, wood, enamel, dentin, bone, hair, rubber. The unit cell of quartz which has specific atomic structure of the lattice which is a tetrahedron built of oxygen atoms around a silicon atom. Each oxygen atom has the same distance to the silicon atom, and the distances between the oxygen atoms are all the same. The change in the position of the atoms due to applied stress leads to the formation of net dipole moments that causes polarization and an electric field, respectively. Man-made piezoelectric materials are crystals that are quartz analogues, ceramics, polymers and composites. There are 32 crystal classes which are divided into the following seven groups: triclinic, monoclinic, orthorhombic, tetragonal, trigonal, hexagonal and cubic. These groups are also associated with the elastic nature of the material where triclinic represents an anisotropic material, orthorhombic represents an orthotropic material and cubic are in most cases isotropic materials. Only 20 out of the 32 classes allow piezoelectric properties. Ten of these classes are polar, i.e. show a spontaneous

polarization without mechanical stress due to a non-vanishing electric dipole moment associated with their unit cell. The remaining 10 classes are not polar, i.e. polarization appears only after applying a mechanical load. There are the following families of man-made ceramics with crystal structure as perovskite: Barium titanate (BaTiO_3) Lead titanate (PbTiO_3); Lead zirconate titanate $\text{Pb}[\text{Zr}(x), \text{Ti}(1-x)]\text{O}_3$, ($0 < x < 1$) — more commonly known as PZT; Potassium niobate (KNbO_3); Lithium niobate (LiNbO_3); Lithium tantalate (LiTaO_3), etc. and other lead-free piezo ceramics. The general chemical formulae of perovskite crystal structure are ABO_3 , where A is a larger metal ion, usually lead Pb or barium Ba, B is a smaller metal ion, usually titanium Ti or zirconium Zr, which shows the crystal structure of a piezoelectric ceramic (BaTiO_3) at temperature above and below Curie point [7].

The problem of power generation has been a big problem for Nigeria and many developing countries for many years. Power generation has been mainly through thermal power plants and hydro sources. Shortage in these sources has made us resort to other means of renewable power generation such as solar and wind energy. The use of these renewable energies produces valuable and sustainable energy to minimize waste. Producing energy is a challenge for current research and development. Renewable energy such as piezoelectricity serves as means of reducing this challenge. Generation of power from piezoelectric energy harvester serves a cheaper means to solve this problem.

The importance of this current research is to develop a model piezoelectric energy harvester which can be scaled up and be used on a large scale at commercial centres or populated areas such as shopping malls, banking halls, praying grounds, football pitches, dance floors, pedestrian bridges. This design fits for a very populated area. The energy gotten from this design can be used in light fittings such as street lights, classroom lights, traffic light etc. in these areas when needed. Today, about 60% to 70% of the Nigerian population does not have access to constant electricity. There is no doubt that the present power crisis afflicting Nigeria will persist unless the government diversifies the energy sources in domestic, commercial, and industrial sectors and adopts new available technologies to increase energy generation. One source of energy that ought to be tapped into is the renewable energy in general. Umeda [8] sought after a device that would eliminate the need to charge up a mobile device before taking it anywhere. The device would charge the mobile device enroute while travelling. To accomplish this, they constructed a piezo-generator that transforms mechanical impact energy to electrical energy by using a steel ball which impacts the generator. They achieved a maximum efficiency of 35% which is higher than that of a solar cell. With decreasing power requirements for sensors, Elvin [9] say that it seems feasible to harvest the power at the source and transmit the information wirelessly to a receiver elsewhere. Ottman [10], attempted to optimize the power transferred by a vibrating piezoelectric transducer to a battery. An AC-DC rectifier is attached to an equivalent circuit of a piezoelectric material since the piezoceramic produces an AC voltage and a battery needs a DC signal. To power the controller and circuitry with vibrations, a larger array of piezoceramics must be used to generate the required power. Hoffmann [11], tried to improve upon the direct charging of a battery across the rectifier circuit. This method is non-optimal, and a converter would be able to optimize the charging process. The optimal duty cycle is also found experimentally. By using the step-down converter with the fixed duty cycle, the harvested energy was increased 325%. Lesieutre [12], developed a stand-alone harvesting system. For low excitation levels, a rectifier charges a battery directly. For high excitation levels, a DC-DC converter was used and results in more than four times the amount of power than without using the converter. Kasyap [13] experimented on a cantilever beam which had a PZT patch attached to it so as to produce an electrical charge. The scientists harvested this vibrational energy and stored it using a flyback converter. Sodano [14] used a PSI-5h4e piezo bonded onto a plate (80 mm \times 40 mm \times 0.095 in.) to charge a capacitor and also a NiMH cell. For the capacitor, they use an adaptation of a circuit designed for a self-powered RF tag (Kymissis [15]). Donelan [16] made an invention relating to generating electricity during walking with minimal human effort. The device harnesses the power of the human gait by tapping the natural braking motion at the end of every stride. The energy harvester device mounts at the knee and selectively engages power generation at the end of the swing phase, thus assisting deceleration of the joint. In his work, Mishra, et al [17], generated electric power from people's footsteps and the pressure applied when walking, which is frittered away. The power producing floor generates power, which is essentially the conversion of kinetic energy into electrical energy. Ming-Hsiang [18] modelled an electricity producing shoe. The shoe body comprises an electricity-producing module and an electricity generator mounted therein. The electricity producing module comprises of a rack, first and

second gears, and a spring buffer that mounts between the first and second gears. The first and second gears are engaged with the rack and an axial gear of the electricity generator respectively. The electricity generator has an electricity output terminal connected to an electric device of the shoe body. As a result, the rack drives the first gear and the second gear drives the axial gear of the electricity generator by means of normal stepping motion of walking for producing electric power and thereby supplying the electric power for the electric device. Sandru [19] reported that the Hefer intersection along the old coastal road of Route 4 in Israel was the place used to test a piezoelectric generator and generated some 2,000 watt-hours of electricity. The setup consists of a ten-meter strip of asphalt, with generators lying underneath, and batteries in the road's proximity. The technology is based on piezoelectric materials that enabled the conversion of mechanical energy exerted by the weight of passing vehicles into electrical energy. Expanding the project to a length of one kilometer along a single lane would produce 200 KWh, while a four-lane highway could produce about 1 MWh – sufficient electricity to provide for the average consumption in 2,500 households. Taliyan [20] developed a device that generated energy that can be stored in a battery. A 100-watt, 230-volt bulb was connected to the battery through an inverter. The device was operated by persons walking over to it. The bulb automatically lights up when the battery reaches its full voltage. The bulb remained lighted till the battery was exhausted. If there is continuous movement of pedestrians over the device, the bulb can be kept lighted continuously. Arjun [21] cited a famous nightclub in London, where the principle of piezoelectricity in making its dance floor was exploited. The dance floor uses piezoelectricity where crystal and ceramics create a charge to generate electricity. The electricity created in this way is used to power parts of the nightclub such as the sound and lighting. Shell Media [22] reported on the football pitch refurbished by Shell at the Federal College of Education (Technical), Akoka, Lagos, Nigeria. The football pitch consists of underground tiles that capture kinetic energy created by the movement of the players. The energy is then stored and combined with power generated by solar panels to operate the new floodlights. This allows the students to play at night and provides a safer and more secure space at the heart of the community. The objective of this research is power generation through footsteps as a source of renewable energy. This generation of electricity (by footsteps) is done with the aid of a piezoelectric energy harvester. This will build knowledge capacity in this aspect of renewable energy.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials

Many materials will be used for the research. These materials are discussed below:

The following are the components needed:

- 10 LEDs of 1.8volts each
- Wood (7.5in X 11.7in)
- 85 Piezoelectric transducers
- 12 Hot guns glue.
- 2 yards Jumper wires
- 1 Vero board
- Soldering lead

Tools Used:

- Hot Glue Gun
- Soldering Iron
- Saw
- Multi-meter
- Razor blade
- Grip/Nose Pliers

PZT (Lead Zirconate Titanate) is the most commonly used piezoelectric material, because the customization of PZT chemical composition allows a wide range of properties. Also, its Curie temperature (i.e. temperature at which it loses its piezoelectric property) is above 200°C making it suitable for use (each PZT having a maximum voltage of 0.172volts). Plywood is used for the base

and platform on which the PZTs will be placed. Plywood is used due to its durability, strength and life span. Its measurement is $190.5 \times 297.2 \text{ mm}^2$. Diodes help to control the direction of current flow (in one direction) and they are also used to convert the AC current to DC current. PZTs produce alternating current and not all appliances run on AC especially for storage. Cork Stacks of thin square cork in groups of 3 are placed on each transducer. Therefore, when a person steps on a board with no stacks, the pressure applied gets equally distributed and hence produces less shearing; however, if a person steps on a board with cork stacks, then the pressure applied gets concentrated on the transducers causing maximum shearing and increasing the potential difference. Light Emitting Diodes (LEDs) are two-lead semiconductor light sources. It is a p-n junction diode that emits light when activated. In this project, we want to light up 10 LEDs. LED has 3volts capacity. Multi meter is used to measure the voltage generated. Equations (1) and (2) are some of the basic equations used in the research.

$$\text{Pressure} = \text{Force} / \text{Area} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Stress} = \text{Force} / \text{Area} \tag{2}$$

2.2. METHODS

When piezoelectric crystal is under pressure, it will produce deformation, the piezoelectric crystal on both sides of the conductive layer will polarize and produce charge and voltage, the piezoelectric crystal can be equivalent to a capacitor and a resistor in parallel, the capacitance is very small, the parallel resistance value is very large [24, 25]. The pressure and the voltage generated by the piezoelectric crystal $v_g(t)$ can be expressed as in equations (3) and (4)

$$V_g(t) = (F(t)/A) \times h/G_{33} \tag{3}$$

or

$$V_g(t) = d_{33} \times F(t)/C_p \tag{4}$$

Where: $F(t)$ =pressure
 A = crystal surface area
 h = crystal thickness
 G_{33} = piezoelectric voltage constant
 d_{33} = the piezoelectric strain constant
 C_p = piezoelectric crystal equivalent capacitance

The expression for C_p is given in equation (5)

$$C_p = k \times A / h \tag{5}$$

Where: k = dielectric constant.

The energy produced by piezoelectric crystal is given in equation (6)

$$E_g = 1/2 \times C_p \times V_g^2 \tag{6}$$

The piezoelectric voltage could be very high, but the piezoelectric equivalent capacitance is small. When the pressure is removed, the charge above the piezoelectric crystal will disappear. While a piezoelectric crystal does generate a voltage when subjected to mechanical stress, this voltage is often not directly usable for many applications due to its low power output and AC nature. The generated voltage is typically small and in the form of a high-voltage, low-current AC signal, which requires further processing for most practical uses.

2.3. Study of the connections

It is necessary to determine the kind of connection that gives appreciable voltage and current. If a force sensor and voltmeter are connected to the series combination, it will be seen that the voltage from a series connection is good but the current obtained is poor, whereas the current from a parallel connection is good but the voltage is poor. From this, it can be concluded to connect the PZTs in series-parallel connection. Hence, connecting in parallel helps reduce the total resistance to minimum. Secondly, series connection produces good voltage and poor current. Parallel connection produces good current and poor voltage. But the problem is rectified in a series-parallel connection where a good voltage as well as current can be obtained.

2.4. Experimental Set-up

The design is required to power LED bulbs. The construction of the piezoelectric human energy harvester was carried out as follows:

- i) Grid was drawn on the wood for proper alignment of the piezoelectric transducers
- ii) The top casings of the piezoelectric transducers were removed
- iii) Piezoelectric transducers were glued to the board using the hot glue gum on intersections of the grid
- iv) The piezoelectric transducers were filled with gum on the piezoelectric part to give it a required height for uniformity and appropriate pressure for activation.
- v) The piezoelectric transducers were grouped into four. Each group consists of 21 piezoelectric transducers connected in series and the four groups were connected in parallel to produce appropriate voltage and currents.
- vi) LEDs were soldered on the Vero board and the terminals of the piezoelectric transducers were connected to the respective terminals of the LEDs
- vii) The piezoelectric energy harvester was tested by stepping on it.

Figures 2a and 2b is the PZT connected and glued to the plywood board.

Figure 2a: PZT connected in series-parallel on the board.

Figure 2b: The LED indicator to indicate current flow when piezoelectric energy harvester is stepped on.

2.5 Problems Encountered

- Terminals of piezoelectric transducers were very fragile; hence a lot of soldering were carried out which lead to decrease in the amount of voltage generated.
- Differences in height of the transducers caused little voltage and current to be generated.

3. Results, Observation and Discussions

3.1 Results

The results of the experiment is presented in Table 1 below. The parameters used for the calculations are stated below.

Voltage of each Piezoelectric Crystal = 0.17 V
 Length of piezoelectric energy harvester = 190.5 mm
 Breadth of piezoelectric energy harvester = 297.2 mm.
 Area of energy harvester = $190.5 \times 297.2 \text{ mm}^2$
 $= 56,616.6 \text{ mm}^2$
 $= 0.0566166 \text{ m}^2$

Tabulated in Table 1 is outcome of the power produced by different categories of people with different weights.

Table 1: Average power generated under different weights

S/N	Mass (kg)	Weight/Force = mg (N) (where $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$)	Pressure = F/A (N/m^2) (where $A = 0.5661279 \text{ m}^2$)	Voltage (V) (multi-meter readings)	Current (A) (multi-meter readings)	Power produced (W) ($P = IV$)
1	60	588.60	10396.94	5.90	0.01	0.059
2	65	637.65	11263.4	8.40	0.02	0.168
3	70	686.70	12129.8	9.30	0.02	0.186
4	75	735.75	13031.5	12.50	0.02	0.250
5	80	784.80	13862.6	15.10	0.04	0.604

Figure 4: Graph of Weight against Power produced.

3.2 Observations and Discussions

- With increasing weight, the amount of voltage produced was increased
- The packing density of the piezoelectric transducer was put into consideration for uniform weight distribution (packing density is a very important consideration in the design of a piezoelectric power generation system. This is because it ensures maximum impact of vibration source on all the transducers used in the design. Higher packing density increases the efficiency of the system by increasing impact of vibration and reduces losses on current carrying conductors used in the design of the system).
- Force needs to be sudden and continuous like in steppings to cause vibrations on the piezoelectric part
- Short circuiting was avoided by using black tape to cover all the appropriate terminals
- Uniform height of the transducers was ensured.

4. CONCLUSION

Energy from human movement was captured and converted into usable electrical power that can be stored and be utilized later. Some LEDs were connected and lit up to demonstrate that human energy had generated electrical power. The amount of power obtained was dependent on the amount of pressure applied on the harvester and the number of PZT utilized in the harvester. As seen from the graph, increase in pressure leads to increase in power. The maximum voltage gotten from the energy harvester was in the series-parallel connection. There were losses in voltages due to some poor connection in soldering some of the wires to the transducers. PZT energy harvester can be applied in a very wide of application especially in every densely populated area. It is one of the cheapest means of renewable energy, that could be so employed. PZT crystals should be used rather than piezoelectric transducers to get more voltages. More crystals should be used for commercial or larger applications. Cork stakes (i.e. equal heights of cylindrical wood) should be used rather than gum, and batteries can be used for storage of the electricity for later use.

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